

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of store atmosphere and promotions on purchase decisions through perceived value in the fashion category at Ramayana department store in Jakarta

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Abstract

The retail industry in Indonesia has shown rapid growth, particularly within the fashion retail sector. This development is marked by the rising and evolving consumer demand for fashion products. Ramayana Department Store, as a key player in the fashion retail market, is currently facing intense competition from various companies offering similar goods. Despite its strong presence, Ramayana has experienced a notable decline in sales and has not yet regained its previous performance level. This study seeks to examine the influence of store atmosphere and sales promotion on consumers' purchase decisions in the fashion category at Ramayana Department Store Jakarta, with perceived value as a mediating variable. A quantitative, explanatory research design was employed, utilizing a questionnaire distributed to 97 respondents selected through purposive non-probability sampling. Data analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) via SmartPLS 4.0. The analysis involved outer and inner model testing to assess construct validity and the relationships among variables. The findings reveal that both store atmosphere and sales promotion significantly and directly influence perceived value and purchase decisions. Additionally, these variables also exert an indirect effect on purchase decisions through perceived value, which serves as a partial mediator. The study suggests areas for improvement at Ramayana, including optimizing store layout and product presentation, strengthening promotional efforts, enhancing value for money, aligning product quality with consumer expectations, adapting to current fashion trends, and expanding online sales channels to improve accessibility.

Keywords: Store Atmosphere; Sales Promotion; Perceived Value; Purchase Decision

1. Introduction

The retail industry in Indonesia, particularly in major urban centers such as Jakarta, is characterized by intense competition. The presence of numerous players, ranging from traditional to modern retail formats, necessitates continuous innovation by each company to maintain competitiveness. According to a report by Euromonitor International (2023), the Indonesian retail market is projected to experience a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 6% through the year 2025.

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Table 1 Retail Market Growth Data in Indonesia

Year	Retail Market Value (Trillion IDR)	Growth (%)
2020	2500	4,5
2021	2600	4,0
2022	2750	5,8
2023	2900	5,5
2024	3100	6,0
2025	3300	6,5

Source : Euromonitor International, 2024

Based on the table above, the retail market in Indonesia has shown growth from 2020 and is projected to continue rising until 2025. This indicates significant potential for businesses in Indonesia, as consumers consistently purchase products to meet their daily needs.

Table 2 Top Brand Index of Department Store Category

No	Brand	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
1	Matahari	50.70%	52.50%	51.70%	51.80%	50.50%
2	Ramayana	12.70%	14.10%	14.60%	15.90%	14.00%
3	Toserba Yogya	3.90%	3.60%	3.80%	3.80%	8.70%

Source : topbrand-award.com, 2024

Table 2. shows that Ramayana has consistently ranked second among Top Brands in Indonesia's retail sector over the past five years. However, in 2024, Ramayana experienced a decline, with its Top Brand Index (TBI) falling by 14%. This decline indicates the presence of factors influencing consumer purchase decisions that may not have been fully addressed by Ramayana.

Purchase decision refers to the process consumers go through when deciding to buy a product or service (12). It is a common action taken by consumers to acquire a product. Purchase decision is an understanding in which consumers recognize their desires and needs for a product, evaluate various influencing factors, identify alternatives, and make a decision to purchase, followed by post-purchase behavior (16).

Source : databoks.katadata.co.id (2022)

Figure 1 Revenue and Profit/Loss of Fashion Retail Companies

Based on data collected from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), it can be observed that in the first semester of 2022, Mitra Adiperkasa (MAP) led in terms of revenue, recording IDR 12,248 billion. MAP also reported the highest profit,

amounting to IDR 1,031 billion. This was followed by Matahari, with revenue of IDR 3,762 billion and a profit of IDR 918.37 billion. At the bottom was Ramayana, with revenue of IDR 1,856 billion and a profit of IDR 286.03 billion. From the presented statistical data, it can be concluded that Ramayana lags behind in competition compared to MAP and Matahari.

Table 3 Target and Actual Performance Data of Ramayana Department Store

Year	Target (Trillion)	Actual (Trillion)	Achievement (%)
2019	Rp5.036.758	Rp5.596.398	111
2020	Rp6.156.038	Rp2.527.951	41
2021	Rp2.907.144	Rp2.592.682	89
2022	Rp3.089.292	Rp2.996.613	97
2023	Rp3.296.274	Rp2.744.427	83

Source : Analyzed Data, 2024

Based on table 3, it can be observed that Ramayana experienced a significant decline in sales in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. However, up to the present, Ramayana has not yet been able to recover to its previous performance levels. Annual sales remain unstable and have yet to meet the sales targets.

Store atmosphere and sales promotion are complementary marketing strategies that influence consumer perceived value and purchasing decisions. A comfortable, attractive store atmosphere invites customers to stay longer and feel happy, while sales promotions provide extra incentives to buy. Together, they enhance positive consumer perceptions, boosting sales volume and customer loyalty.

As of 2023, Ramayana Department Store operates 101 outlets across 54 cities in Indonesia. However, Ramayana's inability to compete effectively in the fashion retail market has led to significant losses at several outlets, forcing their closure to ensure the company's sustainability.

Table 4 Ramayana Department Store Outlet Data

	2020	2021	2022	2023	Summary
Jakarta	17	14	13	13	4 outlet decreased
Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, Bekasi	28	28	27	26	2 outlet decreased
West Java	9	9	10	10	1 outlet added
Central Java	7	7	8	8	1 outlet added
East Java	11	10	10	10	1 outlet added
Sumatera	18	20	19	18	2 outlet added, then 2 outlet decreased
Kalimantan	7	7	7	7	Same amount
Sulawesi	3	3	3	3	Same amount
Bali	2	2	2	2	Same amount
Nusa Tenggara	1	1	1	1	Same amount
Maluku	1	1	1	1	Same amount
Papua	2	2	3	3	1 outlet added

Source : Analyzed Data, 2024

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that over the past four years, Jakarta has experienced the highest number of outlet closures due to losses and inability to sustain competition. Considering the background presented, it is evident

that Ramayana has faced a decline in sales and has yet to meet its business targets. Efforts such as improving store atmosphere and implementing sales promotions have been undertaken to enhance perceived value as a strategy to compete and boost sales.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Consumer Behavior

Consumer Behavior refers to the study of how individuals make decisions to spend their available resources—time, money, and effort—on consumption-related items (15). It involves the processes consumers use to recognize needs, gather information, evaluate alternatives, make purchasing decisions, and assess post-purchase experiences. Consumer behavior is influenced by four main factors: cultural (values, subcultures, traditions), social (reference groups, family, social class), personal (age, occupation, lifestyle, economic conditions, personality), and psychological (motivation, perception, learning, and attitudes). These factors interact to shape consumer preferences, perceptions, and responses to marketing stimuli, ultimately determining purchasing patterns. In this study, consumer behavior is considered a key foundation for analyzing purchase decisions, as it reflects how external influences and internal characteristics drive consumer choices in the retail fashion context.

2.2. Purchase Decisions

Purchase Decision refers to the consumer's process of choosing whether or not to buy a product, including the selection of brand, quantity, purchase time, distribution channel, and payment method (15). The decision-making process generally follows five stages: need recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decision, and post-purchase evaluation. Purchase decisions are influenced by cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors (15), and can be measured through indicators such as product choice, brand choice, distributor choice, purchase timing, purchase quantity, and payment methods.

2.3. Perceived Value

Perceived Value is defined as the consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product based on the trade-off between what is received and what is given (16). It plays a key role in determining consumer preferences and purchase behavior. According to Sweeney and Soutar (2001), perceived value can be assessed through four indicators: emotional value, performance/quality value, social value, and value for money.

2.4. Store Atmosphere

Store Atmosphere represents the environment created by retailers to enhance consumer shopping experiences and influence purchase behavior. It encompasses both interior and exterior elements, such as lighting, layout, aroma, music, and visual merchandising (15, 6). Indicators of store atmosphere include store exterior, general interior, store layout, and interior display.

2.5. Sales Promotion

Sales Promotion refers to short-term incentives designed to stimulate consumer purchases (15). Effective sales promotions can increase sales volume, shift consumer purchase behavior, strengthen brand awareness, and foster customer loyalty. Indicators include sales increase, changes in consumer buying patterns, brand awareness and recall, customer loyalty, distribution channel effectiveness, and consumer perception of promotional value.

2.6. Research Method

This study employs an explanatory quantitative approach to examine the influence of store atmosphere and sales promotion on purchase decisions, mediated by perceived value. The sample consists of 97 respondents—men and women aged 15–64 who have made fashion purchases at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta and experienced promotional activities—selected using a non-probability purposive sampling method. The research utilizes primary data collected through a Likert scale questionnaire (scale 1–5), designed to measure constructs with multiple indicators. Hypothesis testing is conducted using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the SmartPLS 4 software. SEM is applied to assess both direct and indirect relationships between latent variables, with PLS used to predict and validate theoretical constructs. The model evaluation involves two main stages: the outer model, assessing convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability; and the inner model, evaluating the structural path significance using R-square, F-square, and bootstrapping for t-test analysis. Intervening effects of perceived value are also analyzed through indirect effect testing via SmartPLS bootstrapping.

Figure 2 Model Hypothesis

- H1 : There is a suspected influence of Store Atmosphere on Perceived Value among fashion category consumers at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta.
- H2 : There is a suspected influence of Sales Promotion on Perceived Value among fashion category consumers at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta.
- H3 : There is a suspected influence of Perceived Value on Purchase Decision among fashion category consumers at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta.
- H4 : There is a suspected influence of Store Atmosphere on Purchase Decision among fashion category consumers at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta.
- H5 : There is a suspected influence of Sales Promotion on Purchase Decision among fashion category consumers at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta.
- H6 : There is a suspected influence of Store Atmosphere on Purchase Decision mediated by Perceived Value among fashion category consumers at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta.
- H7 : There is a suspected influence of Sales Promotion on Purchase Decision mediated by Perceived Value among fashion category consumers at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta.

3. Results

3.1. Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Measurement model or outer model refers to the relationship between latent construct and each indicator block that measures them.

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

Figure 3 Diagram Path Analysis

3.1.1. Convergent Validity

The initial stage of this study involved testing the indicators within the model to ensure that convergent validity met the established standards. Correlation is considered to have achieved convergent validity if the loading factor value >0.70 and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is >0.50 (10).

Table 5 Outer Loading Result

Indicators	Variable	Loading Factor	Type (as defined)	Notes
SA1	Store Atmosphere	0.792	Reflective	Valid
SA2		0.905	Reflective	Valid
SA3		0.873	Reflective	Valid
SA4		0.758	Reflective	Valid
SP1	Sales Promotion	0.851	Reflective	Valid
SP2		0.896	Reflective	Valid
SP3		0.857	Reflective	Valid
SP4		0.771	Reflective	Valid
PV1	Perceived Value	0.711	Reflective	Valid
PV2		0.819	Reflective	Valid
PV3		0.836	Reflective	Valid
PV4		0.820	Reflective	Valid
PD1	Purchase Decision	0.850	Reflective	Valid
PD2		0.768	Reflective	Valid
PD3		0.780	Reflective	Valid
PD4		0.866	Reflective	Valid
PD5		0.806	Reflective	Valid
PD6		0.701	Reflective	Valid

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

Based on the test results in table 5, it can be observed that all items for each variable exhibit loading factor values >0.70. Therefore, it can be concluded that each item adequately represents the latent variable it measures. The higher the loading factor value, the stronger the relationship between the item and the respective latent variable.

Table 6 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Store Atmosphere (SA)	0.635
Sales Promotion (SP)	0.637
Perceived Value (PV)	0.696
Purchase Decision (PD)	0.714

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

Based on table 6, the AVE values obtained for each variable are >0.50. This indicates that each item is able to explain more than 50% of the variance in the latent variable it represents. An AVE value above 0.50 is considered a good indication of convergent validity, meaning that the items are effective in measuring the latent variable.

3.1.2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is evaluated using two main methods, the Fornell-Larcker criterion and cross-loading analysis. The Fornell-Larcker approach compares the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) with the correlations between constructs, discriminant validity is confirmed if the AVE root is greater than the correlations. Cross-loading analysis checks whether each indicator loads highest on its own construct compared to others, indicating adequate discriminant validity.

Table 7 Fornell-Larcker

	PD	PV	SA	SP
PD	0.797			
PV	0.654	0.798		
SA	0.487	0.480	0.834	
SP	0.618	0.466	0.354	0.845

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

The analysis results indicate that the square roots of the AVE values for each construct (PD = 0.797; PV = 0.798; SA = 0.834; SP = 0.845) are higher than the correlations between the constructs. This demonstrates that each construct in the model meets discriminant validity, clearly measuring distinct concepts.

Table 8 Cross Loadings

	PD	PV	SA	SP
PD1	0.850	0.505	0.379	0.615
PD2	0.768	0.445	0.368	0.492
PD3	0.780	0.488	0.305	0.438
PD4	0.866	0.522	0.421	0.545
PD5	0.806	0.625	0.462	0.492
PD6	0.701	0.529	0.381	0.344
PV1	0.476	0.711	0.319	0.347
PV2	0.421	0.819	0.338	0.259
PV3	0.591	0.836	0.527	0.391
PV4	0.564	0.820	0.316	0.461
SA1	0.358	0.386	0.792	0.316
SA2	0.491	0.408	0.905	0.349
SA3	0.440	0.401	0.873	0.283
SA4	0.319	0.412	0.758	0.228
SP1	0.510	0.419	0.281	0.851
SP2	0.554	0.351	0.292	0.896
SP3	0.553	0.418	0.321	0.857
SP4	0.467	0.385	0.303	0.771

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

Based on the data presented in table 8, it can be seen that each measurement item has a higher cross-loading value and shows a stronger correlation with its respective variable compared to other variables. For example, the cross-loading

value of item PD1 on the PD variable is 0.850, while on the PV, SA, and SP variables it is 0.505, 0.379, and 0.615, respectively. This demonstrates that PD1 is more dominant in measuring the PD variable itself than the others. Therefore, it can be concluded that the discriminant validity criteria have been met.

3.1.3. Composite Reliability

Reliability testing in this study was conducted using two main indicators: composite reliability and Cronbach’s alpha. These measures assess how consistently and accurately the indicators reflect their respective constructs. Cronbach’s alpha evaluates internal consistency among items, while composite reliability assesses overall construct reliability. A construct is considered reliable if both values >0.70 otherwise, it is deemed unreliable.

Table 9 Composite Reliability and Cronbach’s Alpha

	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Composite Reliability (rho_c)</i>
PD	0.884	0.912
PV	0.810	0.875
SA	0.852	0.901
SP	0.866	0.909

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

Based on Table 3.5, all variables in this study (PD, PV, SA, and SP) have Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability values above 0.70. This indicates that all constructs in the model demonstrate a high level of reliability, meaning the indicators for each variable can be considered reliable.

3.2. Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model)

Inner model or structural model testing is used to predict the relationship that occurs between variables in a research model. This inner model test includes testing the coefficient of determination (R-Square).

Table 10 R-square Result

	<i>R-square</i>
<i>Store Atmosphere and Sales Promotion -> Purchase Decision</i>	0.572
<i>Store Atmosphere and Sales Promotion -> Perceived Value</i>	0.331

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

Based on the table above, there are two endogenous (dependent) variables in this research model that are influenced by exogenous (independent) variables, there is purchase decision with an R-square value of 0.572 and perceived value with an R-square value of 0.331. The test results indicate that store atmosphere and sales promotion contribute 57.2% to purchase decision, while the remaining 42.8% is influenced by other variables not included in this study. Meanwhile, store atmosphere and sales promotion account for 33.1% of the perceived value, with the remaining 66.9% influenced by other external variables. According to Ghozali (2020), research models can be categorized as strong (≥ 0.75), moderate (0.26–0.74), and weak (≤ 0.25). Based on this classification, the R-square values for purchase decision (0.572) and perceived value (0.331) fall into the moderate category.

3.3. Hypothesis Test

The hypothesis testing in this study was conducted using the bootstrapping method through the SmartPLS version 4.0 statistical software. This method is used to assess the magnitude of both direct and indirect effects between variables. The hypothesis testing process was carried out in two stages: evaluation of the direct effect and evaluation of the indirect effect. In this analysis, the evaluation criteria include:

- T-Statistics > 1.96 indicates a significant relationship at a 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$).
- P-Values < 0.05 also indicate a significant relationship at the 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$).

If the t-statistic value exceeds the critical value from the t-table, it can be concluded that the independent variable has a significant influence on the dependent variable. Likewise, if the p-value is less than 0.05, the independent variable is considered to have a significant impact on the dependent variable. The following presents the results of the model analysis in this study:

Figure 4 Diagram Path Analysis Bootstrapping

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

3.3.1. Direct Effect

The first stage of this analysis is to examine the direct effect between the variables *store atmosphere* and *sales promotion* on *purchase decision*. The following table presents the direct effect results obtained from the path coefficients output and P-values.

Table 11 Direct Effect on Output Path Coefficients

Independent Variables and Dependent Variable	Path Coeff	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T statistics	P values	Notes
Store Atmosphere -> Perceived Value	0.361	0.362	0.101	3.561	0.000	H1 Accepted
Sales Promotion -> Perceived Value	0.338	0.345	0.110	3.075	0.002	H2 Accepted
Perceived Value -> Purchase Decision	0.402	0.404	0.110	3.657	0.000	H3 Accepted
Store Atmosphere -> Purchase Decision	0.162	0.164	0.082	1.980	0.048	H4 Accepted
Sales Promotion -> Purchase Decision	0.373	0.370	0.115	3.245	0.001	H5 Accepted

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

Based on the path coefficients presented in table 11, all hypotheses (H1 to H5) were supported. Store atmosphere and sales promotion both have significant positive effects on perceived value, with path coefficients of 0.361 and 0.338, respectively. Perceived value also significantly influences purchase decisions (path coefficient = 0.402). Additionally, store atmosphere and sales promotion directly and positively impact purchase decisions, with path coefficients of 0.162 and 0.373, respectively. All results show t-statistics greater than 1.96 and p-values below 0.05, indicating that these relationships are statistically significant for fashion consumers at Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta.

3.3.2. Indirect Effect

The next stage of this analysis is to examine the indirect effects of store atmosphere and sales promotion on purchase decisions through perceived value as an intervening variable. The following table presents the indirect effect results based on path coefficients and p-values obtained from the output.

Table 12 Output Specific Indirect Effects

Independent Variables and Dependent Variable	Path Coeff	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T statistics	P values	Notes
Store Atmosphere -> Perceived Value -> Purchase Decision	0.145	0.145	0.055	2.639	0.008	H6 Accepted
Sales Promotion -> Perceived Value -> Purchase Decision	0.136	0.143	0.067	2.034	0.042	H7 Accepted

Source: Data Processed using Smart-PLS, 2025

The findings from the specific indirect effects analysis in table 12 indicate that both store atmosphere and sales promotion have a positive and significant indirect influence on purchase decisions through perceived value. Store atmosphere shows a path coefficient of 0.145, with a t-statistic of 2.639 and a p-value of 0.008, while sales promotion has a path coefficient of 0.136, a t-statistic of 2.034, and a p-value of 0.042. These results confirm that perceived value effectively mediates the impact of store atmosphere and sales promotion on the purchase decisions of Ramayana Department Store fashion consumers in Jakarta.

4. Discussion

This research aimed to identify the direct and indirect influences between independent, dependent, and intervening variables using SmartPLS 4.0. The following sections delve into the detailed findings. Store atmosphere significantly influences how consumers perceive their overall shopping experience (13). A well-designed store can enhance perceptions of product quality and provide higher emotional and hedonic value (3). Our findings, consistent with Sianturi (2025), show a direct, positive, and significant effect of store atmosphere on perceived value at Ramayana Department Store. The general interior and exterior appearance of Ramayana stores were highly rated by respondents, indicating successful efforts in creating a positive impression and recognizable brand presence. However, store layout (e.g., rack placement, aisles, cashiers) and interior display (product arrangement) still need improvement to enhance customer movement and product discovery, which are crucial for optimizing perceived value.

Sales promotions, such as discounts and coupons, are marketing incentives designed to encourage short-term purchases (4). Consumers often perceive that products with promotions offer additional utility, thus increasing perceived value (7). Our research, aligning with Tristanto and Iswati (2025), confirms a direct, positive, and significant impact of sales promotion on perceived value at Ramayana. Respondents highly rated how promotions aided brand recall and acknowledged Ramayana's effectiveness as a distribution channel for fashion products, as well as the alignment of promotion programs with their expectations. Nevertheless, aspects related to consumer purchasing patterns during promotions were below average, indicating a need for improvement to prevent a decline in perceived value.

Perceived value is a consumer's overall evaluation of a product's benefits versus its sacrifices (20). Consumers tend to choose products they believe offer the best value, whether functional, emotional, social, or economic (8). Our findings, supporting Hanaysha (2018), demonstrate a direct, positive, and significant relationship between perceived value and purchase decisions. Respondents highly rated the product quality against expected standards and the suitability of products with social values (trends, norms). However, customer feelings after purchasing (e.g., satisfaction level) and the perceived value for money (product quality versus price) were rated below average. Addressing these aspects is vital for boosting purchase decisions.

Store atmosphere can create specific emotional effects that influence consumer perception and behavior (13). Elements like lighting and color can enhance visual appeal and affect consumer mood, encouraging purchases (5). Our study, consistent with Arianto and Rahayu (2022), shows a direct, positive, and significant effect of store atmosphere on purchase decisions. Ramayana's general interior and exterior effectively create a good impression and attract

consumers. However, similar to the findings for perceived value, store layout (related to customer movement) and interior display (related to product discovery) need refinement to further enhance purchase decisions.

Sales promotions aim to attract consumer attention and boost sales through various techniques like discounts and free samples (15). Promotions can add value, prompting immediate purchases (18). Our results, in line with Arianto and Rahayu (2022), indicate a direct, positive, and significant impact of sales promotion on purchase decisions. Promotions helped consumers recall brands, and Ramayana was effective as a fashion product distributor, with promotion programs meeting consumer expectations. Yet, consumer purchasing patterns during promotions remain an area for improvement to prevent a decrease in purchase decisions. Store atmosphere significantly influences purchase decisions, and this relationship is mediated by perceived value. A comfortable store environment, created by physical elements like lighting and layout, increases perceived value, which in turn drives purchases (13). Our findings, mirroring Sianturi (2025), confirm that perceived value partially mediates the relationship between store atmosphere and purchase decisions. While store atmosphere directly influences purchase decisions, its impact is optimized when supported by perceived value, as evidenced by a higher total effect. Thus, enhancing both store atmosphere and perceived value leads to more optimal purchase decisions.

Perceived value, formed by comparing benefits received with sacrifices made (20), mediates the relationship between sales promotion and purchase decisions. Effective promotions can make consumers perceive products as more advantageous, thereby encouraging purchases (15). Our study, consistent with Tristanto and Iswati (2025), confirms that perceived value partially mediates the relationship between sales promotion and purchase decisions. Sales promotion directly impacts purchase decisions, but its role is optimized when perceived value acts as a mediator, indicated by a higher total effect. Therefore, integrating strong sales promotions with a focus on perceived value will yield more optimal purchase outcomes. forward.

5. Conclusion

This Based on the research conducted on the Influence of Store Atmosphere and Sales Promotion on Consumer Purchase Decisions at Ramayana Department Store (Fashion Category) in Jakarta, with Perceived Value as an Intervening Variable, involving 97 respondents, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Store Atmosphere (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value (Z) for fashion category consumers of Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta. This indicates that store atmosphere influences perceived value.
- Sales Promotion (X2) has a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value (Z) for fashion category consumers of Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta. This indicates that sales promotion influences perceived value.
- Perceived Value (Z) has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision (Y) for fashion category consumers of Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta. This indicates that perceived value influences purchase decisions.
- Store Atmosphere (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision (Y) for fashion category consumers of Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta. This indicates that store atmosphere influences purchase decisions.
- Sales Promotion (X2) has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision (Y) for fashion category consumers of Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta. This indicates that sales promotion influences purchase decisions.
- Store Atmosphere (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision (Y) through Perceived Value (Z) for fashion category consumers of Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta. Perceived value acts as a mediating variable with partial mediation.
- Sales Promotion (X2) has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision (Y) through Perceived Value (Z) for fashion category consumers of Ramayana Department Store in Jakarta. Perceived value acts as a mediating variable with partial mediation.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the research and the conclusions that have been obtained, there are several suggestions from researchers that can be used by Ramayana Department Store as input in efforts to increase purchase decisions. Here are some suggestions from researcher:

- While the **store atmosphere** is generally appealing, Ramayana should optimize its **store layout** with wider aisles, clear pathways, and strategically placed racks to improve customer movement and comfort, potentially

increasing visit duration and purchase volume. Additionally, enhancing **interior display** through clear categorization and large informational signs for each product section will make it easier for customers to find products, creating a more efficient shopping experience.

- Regarding **sales promotion**, Ramayana needs to refine its strategies. By conducting thorough market research, the company can design more tailored promotions (e.g., discounts, bundling, buy-one-get-one offers) that effectively drive higher purchase quantities. This also involves managing a structured promotion calendar, accurately segmenting target markets, and leveraging historical purchase data to determine optimal promotion timing and types. Crucially, Ramayana must ensure consistent product stock availability during promotions to prevent customer dissatisfaction.
- To elevate **perceived value**, Ramayana should focus on improving **emotional value** and **value for money**. Managing customer expectations from the outset by providing clear and honest product information (on labels and via trained staff) will foster positive feelings post-purchase. Implementing after-sales service, loyalty programs, and customer feedback channels can further contribute to this. Furthermore, Ramayana should more effectively curate product partners and suppliers to ensure all items meet minimum quality standards (materials, comfort, design), and adopt value-based pricing strategies that consider consumer perception rather than solely focusing on profit margins.
- To boost **purchase decisions**, Ramayana needs to address **brand choice** and **accessibility**. Actively evaluating and adjusting its brand portfolio by understanding trending brands and maintaining diverse options will cater to various consumer preferences; collaborating with competitive local brands can also enhance appeal. For accessibility, Ramayana should improve physical connectivity by enhancing parking and ensuring clear directional signs. Integrating with online transportation and delivery services, along with developing a robust online sales channel with fast and reliable delivery, will provide convenience for customers with limited mobility or those residing further from the store.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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